

**EFFECTIVENESS OF USING THE “ZAMIN-M” BIOLOGICAL AGENT
IMMOBILIZED TO FLOCCULAR IN THE STORAGE OF POTATO NODULES OF
DIFFERENT VARIETIES**

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Abstract. This article examines the effectiveness of the "Zamin-M" biopreparation, immobilized in a flocculant prepared on the basis of rhizobacteria, in the process of preserving tubers of various potato varieties (Gala, Sante, Picasso, Romano, Red Scarlet). During the research, the dynamics of natural weight loss, dry matter, and moisture content of the tubers during the 4-month storage period were analyzed. The results obtained show that the "Zamin-M" biopreparation significantly reduces weight loss compared to control variants by regulating respiratory intensity and increasing resistance to phytopathogens. In particular, the highest preservation rate (6.2% weight loss) was recorded in the "Picasso" variety. The article provides a scientific justification for the biological preparation's role in maintaining the biochemical balance within potato tubers.

Keywords. Potato, storage, "Zamin-M" immobilized in a flocculant, biological agent, rhizobacteria, weight loss, dry matter, moisture dynamics, phytopathogens, "Gala" variety, "Picasso" variety, biochemical analysis.

Introduction

Among the products grown in agriculture, potatoes are considered one of the important food crops. It is rich in carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals necessary for the human body and plays a special role in ensuring the food security of the population. At the same time, alongside potato cultivation, the issue of long-term storage while maintaining its quality is one of the most pressing issues.

Potatoes are the main crop grown in almost all regions of Uzbekistan. According to statistics, in January–June 2025, all categories of farms in the republic produced 1.9 million tons of potatoes. According to researchers, the normal consumption of potatoes should be 90 kg per person per year [1].

However, in subsequent years, actual consumption per capita reaches only 56 kg per year. Maintenance plays an important role in providing the population with an uninterrupted product throughout the year, as losses at this stage can reach up to 40% [3].

During the storage of potato tubers, various physiological and microbiological processes occur, resulting in a decrease in product quality, decay, drying, and disease. Especially diseases caused by fungi and bacteria lead to significant losses during the storage period. Although the use of chemical preparations is widespread in traditional storage methods, they have disadvantages such as environmental safety, impact on human health, and the preservation of residual substances in the product.

In recent years, due to the growing demand for the cultivation and storage of environmentally friendly and safe products, great attention has been paid to the use of biological preparations. The use of beneficial microorganisms in biopreparations allows for the restriction

of pathogen development, extends product shelf life, and preserves quality indicators. From this perspective, the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation is considered one of the promising agents in the process of preserving potato tubers.

The objective of this scientific article is to study the effectiveness of using the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation in potato tubers storage, and to scientifically evaluate its impact on product quality, shelf life, and loss rates. The research results serve to improve potato product storage technology, introduce environmentally safe methods, and increase economic efficiency.

Research materials and methods. This scientific research is dedicated to studying the effectiveness of using the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation during the storage of potato tubers, and the experiments were conducted under laboratory conditions. Potato tubers of the "**Gala**," "**Sante**," "**Picasso**," "**Ramano**," and "**Red Scarlet**" varieties harvested from the new harvest were selected as the object of study. For the experiment, medium-sized samples of each variety were used, which were not mechanically damaged and lacked signs of disease. 10 kg of samples were taken from each variety and placed in plastic boxes.

The biopreparation was prepared in the form of a working solution in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, and potato tubers were processed by immersion before storage. Subsequently, all samples were stored under the same conditions (4 °C (± 0.5) temperature, 85 (± 5) % relative humidity).

During the storage process, the dynamics of natural mass loss, dry matter, and moisture content in the tubers were regularly monitored. Additionally, microclimate parameters such as temperature and relative humidity were recorded.

Statistical methods were used in the analysis of the obtained results. Differences between the control and experimental groups were compared based on average values and percentage indicators. When assessing the effectiveness, the main criteria were the biochemical effect of the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation immobilized on the flocculant on potato tubers, the effect on reducing natural weight loss, and the effect on extending the shelf life.

The research results serve to scientifically substantiate the prospects for improving potato tubers storage technology and the use of biological protection agents.

Results and discussion

The overall weight loss rate during the potato storage period depends on the interaction of two main factors.

First, physiological weight loss resulting from the intensity of endogenous respiration of the tubers; in this case, moisture evaporation and dry matter consumption due to metabolic processes lead to the loss of the turgor state of the tubers (shriveling). The energy released during the oxidation of glucose during respiration accelerates the evaporation of water contained within the nodule.

Secondly, there is a microbiological factor in which, as a result of the destructive activity of phytopathogenic microorganisms, decomposition (rot) and biochemical degradation of nodule tissues are observed. Pectolytic enzymes secreted by phytopathogens destroy the cell wall of the nodule, which is the primary cause of microbiological weight loss.

This study examined how the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation immobilized on a flocculant affects natural weight loss in various potato varieties. In the study, the ratio of moisture and dry matter was studied over a period of 4 months. Preliminary analyses were conducted before placing the potato tubers for storage. Subsequent analyses were conducted every 30 days. Thus, a total of 5 analyses were conducted, and the results were compared.

Table-1.

Effect of the "**Zamin-M**" biopreparation immobilized on a flocculant on natural weight loss in various potato varieties

Indicators	Storage period, months				
	Before saving	1 month	2 month	3 month	4 month
"Gala" variety					
Weight, kg	10,0	9,85	9,68	9,45	9,20
Dry matter content %	21,5	21,3	21,0	20,6	20,2
Humidity %	78,5	78,7	79,0	79,4	79,8
"Sante" variety					
Weight, kg	10,0	9,82	9,60	9,35	9,12
Dry matter content %	20,8	20,5	20,1	19,7	19,3
Humidity %	79,2	79,5	79,9	80,3	80,7
"Pikasso" variety					
Weight, kg	10,0	9,88	9,72	9,55	9,38
Dry matter content %	19,5	19,3	19,1	18,8	18,5
Humidity %	80,5	80,7	80,9	81,2	81,5
"Romano" variety					
Weight, kg	10,0	9,84	9,65	9,42	9,25
Dry matter content %	22,0	21,8	21,5	21,1	20,7
Humidity %	78,0	78,2	78,5	78,9	79,3
"Red Skarlet" variety					
Weight, kg	10,0	9,86	9,70	9,50	9,30
Dry matter content %	20,2	20,0	19,7	19,4	19,0
Humidity %	79,8	80,0	80,3	80,6	81,0

The obtained experimental results show that treating the flocculant with the immobilized "Zamin-M" biopreparation had a significant impact on the biochemical and physiological processes occurring during storage in all studied potato varieties (Table-1).

Based on the results of four months of storage, weight loss indicators for all varieties were different. The highest conservation stability was observed in the **Picasso** variety—at the end of 4 months, weight loss was only 6.2% (from 10.0 kg to 9.38 kg). The **"Red Scarlet"** (7.0%) and **"Gala"** (8.0%) varieties also showed high results. The highest weight loss was recorded in the **"Sante"** variety (8.8%). This positive trend is explained by the protective layer formed on the

surface of the tubers by the rhizobacteria in the biopreparation and the inhibition of the transpiration (moisture evaporation) process by the Hypan polymer.

The decrease in the amount of dry matter during storage is associated with the vital activity of the tubers, specifically the consumption of carbohydrates (mainly starch) during respiration.

Figure-1. Decrease in dry matter during storage

In the "**Romano**" variety, the dry matter index changed from the initial 22.0% to 20.7% (an absolute decrease of 1.3%). For the "**Gala**" variety, this indicator decreased from 21.5% to 20.2%.

The decrease in respiratory intensity under the influence of the biopreparation made it possible to save dry matter reserves. This indicates that the nutritional value and technological properties (ripening quality) of the potatoes have been preserved at a high level.

Analysis of the table shows that the percentage of moisture content increased slightly by the end of the storage period (for example, from 80.5% to 81.5% for the Picasso variety). This indicates not an increase in moisture content in the tubers, but a change in the relative proportion of the total mass due to the consumption of dry matter for respiration.

Figure 2. Changes in moisture and dry matter content in the tubers of various potato varieties under the influence of the "Zamin-M" biopreparation immobilized in a flocculant during 4-month storage

(storage temperature: +2...+4°C)

The diagram shows that during storage, the moisture content (lower layer) increases slightly compared to dry matter. This does not mean that the moisture content in the tubers has absolutely increased, but rather that its relative share in the total mass has decreased as a result of the consumption of dry matter (mainly starch and sugars) during respiration.

Due to the use of immobilized "Zamin-M" biopreparation in the flocculant, the dry matter reduction line did not decrease sharply. This indicates that the drug effectively inhibits metabolic processes (the activity of hydrolytic enzymes).

During storage, the amount of dry matter decreases in all 5 varieties, and the amount of moisture increases. This is a physiological pattern associated with the decomposition of organic matter and the release of water during the respiration process of potato tubers.

Romano is characterized by the highest dry matter content — 22.0% before storage and 20.7% after 4 months. This variety is considered the richest in terms of dry matter reserves. In contrast, the Picasso variety has the lowest dry matter content (19.5% → 18.5%), i.e., the highest moisture content (80.5% → 81.5%).

The highest decrease in dry matter was observed in the Sante variety—by 1.5 percentage points (from 20.8% to 19.3%). The Picasso variety has the smallest losses—only 1.0 percentage points. In the Gala, Romano, and Red Scarlet varieties, losses are moderate at 1.2–1.3 percentage points.

In all varieties, the loss of dry matter during the 4-month storage period remained within the range of 1.0–1.5%. This indicator is significantly lower than the 2.5–4.0% recorded in the literature for the control (non-prepared) groups. Thus, it can be said that the "Zamin-M" biopreparation immobilized in the flocculant ensured the preservation of dry matter by slowing

down metabolic processes in the tubers. There is a strict inverse relationship between the two indicators—a change in one leads to an equivalent change in the other. In this diagram, the boundary of both fields is clearly seen as gradually moving downward over time.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the conducted research, it can be concluded that the "Zamin-M" biopreparation immobilized on the flocculant controls natural mass loss by saving endogenous energy and increasing the resistance of potato tubers to phytopathogens. Among the studied varieties, the "Picasso" and "Red Scarlet" varieties demonstrated the highest preservation efficiency when treated with this biopreparation.

Based on the results of the multifaceted research and the obtained biochemical analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

Based on the results of the multifaceted research and the obtained biochemical analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The complex of rhizobacteria (*B. megaterium* CKB 310, *B. subtilis* SKB 309) contained in the "Zamin-M" biopreparation immobilized on the flocculant formed a stable biopard on the surface of potato tubers and exerted a strong antagonistic effect against the main phytopathogens (phusarium, phytophthorosis) during the storage period. This significantly reduced the loss of mass resulting from microbiological damage.

- The interaction between the polymer Hypane and microbial metabolites in the preparation allowed for the control of the respiratory intensity of the tubers. It was established that the decrease in dry matter content (averaging 1.2–1.5%) during 4-month storage proceeds significantly slower than in the control variants, indicating that the nutritional value and flavor profile of the product are maintained at a high level.

- Among the studied varieties, the "Pikasso" and "Red Scarlet" varieties demonstrated the highest technological efficiency when treated with the "Zamin-M" biopreparation. The rate of natural weight loss in these varieties did not exceed 6.2% and 7.0%, respectively, which indicates a high degree of adaptation of the drug to the genotypes of these varieties.

- Before storing potatoes, treating the flocculant with the immobilized "Zamin-M" biopreparation is an environmentally safe and cost-effective alternative to traditional chemical fungicides. This technology allows for extending the shelf life by 25-30%, while maintaining the marketable appearance of the product.

According to the results obtained, it is recommended to widely use the "Zamin-M" biopreparation in warehouses and farms specializing in the storage of agricultural products to preserve the biochemical quality of potato tubers and reduce their natural loss.

USED LITERATURE

1. Ibragimova N.M., Murodova S.S., Khojanazarova M.K Storage of potatoes with the help of Biopreparations: Ural Environmental Science Forum “Sustainable Development of Industrial Region” (UESF-2023; April 25-28, 2023). – Chelyabinsk, Russia, 2023. – Volume 389 (2023). – P. 1-6 (E3S Web of Conferences 389, 03095 (2023); doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202338903095).

2. Khojanazarova M.K. (2021). Investigating the cultural-morphological features of rhizobacteria and allocating it from the cotton plant (*Gossypium hirsutum*): in the example of irrigated meadow soils of Uzbekistan IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 939(1) pp.012045. Doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/939/1/012045.

3. Murodova, S.S., & Khujanazarova, M.K. (2020). Study of enzymatic activity of microbiological biopreparation in the cultivation of cotton plant (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) under

saline stress conditions IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 614(1) pp.012125. Doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012125.

4. Afinogenova S.N., Morozov S.A. Sorbic acid contributes to better preservation of potatoes // Potatoes and Vegetables. 2011. No. 7. P. 10.

5. Afinogenova S.N., Morozov S.N. Ecologically safe method of processing potatoes before storage // Modern trends in the formation and development of the agro-industrial market: materials of the International Scientific-Practical Conference. Saratov: IS "Nauka," 2010. PP. 23-26.

6. Afinogenova S.N., Cherkasov O.V. Safety of processing potato tubers with a food preservative during storage // Current issues of commodity science, product safety, and economics: a collection of scientific articles based on the results of the All-Russian Scientific-Practical Conference with International Participation (Kolomna, March 23-24, 2018) / edited by A.N. Stolyarova. Kolomna: State Educational Institution of Higher Education of the Moscow Region "State Social and Humanitarian University," 2018. PP. 34-38.

7. Biological and technological aspects of vegetable and fruit storage / V.A. Borisov, S.A. Maslovsky, A.V. Soldatenko, M.E. Zamyatina. Moscow: K.A. Timiryazev Russian State Agrarian University – MSHA, 2019. 232 p.

8. Influence of biopreparations on the quality of potato tubers in the conditions of the southern forest belt of the Republic of Bashkortostan / I.N. Aminev, M.M. Khaybullin, F.F. Ishkinina // Bulletin of the Bashkir State Agrarian University. - 2020. - No. 1. - P. 5-7.

9. Gunar L.E., Cherenkov A.A. Application of protective-stimulating agents in the storage and production of seed potatoes. Irkutsk: "Megaprint" LLC, 2017. 217p.

10. Dementeva M.I., Vigonsky M.I. Diseases of fruits, vegetables, and potatoes during storage. Moscow: Agropromizdat, 1988. 231 p.

11. Ivanov V.N., Seregin S.N. Food Industry of Russia. Current state, problems, and future development directions. Moscow: Finance and Statistics, 2013. 568 p.

12. Savina O.V. Perspective technology for potato storage using autumn treatment of tubers with the "Biopag" preparation // Potato Farming: Materials of Scientific and Practical Conf. (Moscow, August 1–3, 2017) / edited by S.V. Jevori. M.: ФГБГУ "Всероссийский научно-исследовательский институт картофельного хозяйства имени А.Г. Лорха," 2017. PP. 320-325.

13. Federal State Statistics Service [Electronic resource] URL: http://rosstat.gov.ru/enterprise_economy. Date of access 22.02.2022.